

EVALUATION OF SYNERGISTIC EFFECTS OF EUGENOL AND HYDROXYCHAVICOL FORMULATED WITH SELECTED ANTIBIOTICS ON THE GROWTH OF ESCHERICHIA COLI AND STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS

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Abstract

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) represents one of the most persistent and critical threats to global public health, significantly undermining the effectiveness of conventional antimicrobial therapies. The rapid decline in antibiotic efficacy necessitates the development of safe and innovative strategies to combat resistant pathogens. One promising approach involves the synergistic use of bioactive natural compounds in combination with existing antimicrobial agents to enhance therapeutic effectiveness. In this study, a total of fifty-five laboratory-confirmed bacterial isolates obtained from Rawalpindi Teaching Hospital, Pakistan, were screened. Five representative strains from each group susceptible Escherichia coli, multidrug-resistant (MDR) E. coli, methicillin-sensitive Staphylococcus aureus (MSSA), and methicillin-resistant S. aureus (MRSA) along with reference strains E. coli ATCC 8739 and S. aureus ATCC 6538, were evaluated at BJ Micro Lab. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed according to CLSI and EUCAST guidelines. In-vitro efficacy was assessed using broth micro-dilution for minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), agar assay for minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC), bacterial growth kinetics analysis, checkerboard synergy assays, and determination of MBC values for combined formulations. The synergistic potential of eugenol and hydroxychavicol in combination with azithromycin, cefixime, and ciprofloxacin was investigated. MDR E. coli and MRSA strains demonstrated strong synergistic interactions across all antimicrobial combinations, with Σ FICI values <0.5 . MSSA isolates exhibited an additive interaction for the hydroxychavicol-cefixime combination (Σ FICI = 0.511), while susceptible E. coli strains showed additive effects for eugenol combined with azithromycin (Σ FICI = 0.614) and ciprofloxacin (Σ FICI = 0.738). The reference strain E. coli ATCC 8739 displayed indifferent interactions with ciprofloxacin in combination with both eugenol (Σ FICI = 2.240) and hydroxychavicol (Σ FICI = 1.060), but additive interactions with eugenol-azithromycin (Σ FICI = 0.511) and eugenol-cefixime (Σ FICI = 0.730). Staphylococcus aureus ATCC 6538 showed an additive interaction with the hydroxychavicol-azithromycin combination (Σ FICI = 0.543). Growth kinetics analysis revealed a strong linear correlation between bacterial growth density and

time for both reference strains across varying antimicrobial concentrations, indicating an inverse relationship between antimicrobial concentration and bacterial growth response. MDR E. coli and MRSA isolates exhibited the highest reductions in MBC values, ranging from 9- to >12-fold across all antimicrobial combinations. In contrast, susceptible E. coli and MSSA isolates demonstrated MBC reductions ranging from 7- to 11-fold, while reference strains showed the lowest MBC reductions among all tested groups. These findings highlight the significant potential of eugenol and hydroxychavicol as effective antibiotic adjuvants, particularly against multidrug-resistant bacterial pathogens, offering a promising strategy to address the growing challenge of antimicrobial resistance.

1- Introduction:

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has emerged as one of the most formidable challenges confronting modern medicine and global public health. The rapid rise of resistant bacterial pathogens has severely compromised the effectiveness of existing antimicrobial agents, leading to prolonged infections, increased mortality rates, and escalating healthcare expenditures. According to global surveillance reports, resistance to commonly prescribed antibiotics is increasing at an alarming rate, particularly among Gram-negative and Gram-positive pathogens that are responsible for a wide spectrum of community-acquired and nosocomial infections. Among these, *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* remain two of the most clinically significant bacterial species due to their high prevalence, genetic adaptability, and ability to acquire multidrug resistance. *Escherichia coli* is a major causative agent of urinary tract infections, bloodstream infections, gastrointestinal diseases, and neonatal meningitis, while *Staphylococcus aureus* is frequently associated with skin and soft tissue infections, pneumonia, endocarditis, and device-associated infections. The emergence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) *E. coli* and methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) has significantly narrowed available therapeutic options, often necessitating the use of last-resort antibiotics with higher toxicity profiles [1]. Resistance mechanisms such as enzymatic antibiotic degradation, target site modification, efflux pump overexpression, reduced membrane permeability, and biofilm formation collectively contribute to treatment failure and recurrent infections. These challenges underscore the urgent need for alternative

therapeutic strategies capable of restoring antibiotic efficacy and mitigating resistance development. The discovery and development of new antibiotics have not kept pace with the rapid evolution of resistant bacteria. Economic constraints, lengthy regulatory processes, and diminishing pharmaceutical investment have resulted in a stagnating antibiotic pipeline. Consequently, current research efforts have increasingly focused on antibiotic-sparing strategies, including combination therapies, drug repurposing, and the use of resistance-modifying agents. Combination therapy, in particular, offers a promising approach by exploiting synergistic interactions between agents to enhance antibacterial activity, reduce required drug concentrations, minimize adverse effects, and potentially suppress the emergence of resistance [2]. Synergy-based approaches are especially attractive when they involve compounds that are safe, cost-effective, and readily available. In this context, plant-derived bioactive compounds have gained substantial attention as potential antimicrobial agents and antibiotic adjuvants. Medicinal plants have been used for centuries in traditional healthcare systems, and modern scientific investigations have validated the antimicrobial properties of numerous phytochemicals. Among these, phenolic compounds are of particular interest due to their broad-spectrum antibacterial activity and diverse mechanisms of action. These compounds are known to disrupt bacterial cell membranes, interfere with enzymatic processes, alter metabolic pathways, and modulate bacterial stress responses, thereby sensitizing pathogens to conventional antibiotics. Eugenol, a phenylpropanoid

compound predominantly found in clove oil (*Syzygium aromaticum*), exhibits well-documented antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties. Its antimicrobial activity is primarily attributed to membrane destabilization, increased permeability, and interference with energy metabolism [3]. Hydroxychavicol, a major phenolic constituent of Piper betle leaves, has demonstrated potent antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, including resistant strains. Hydroxychavicol has been reported to induce oxidative stress, disrupt membrane integrity, and inhibit key bacterial enzymes, making it an attractive candidate for combination therapy with antibiotics. Previous studies have reported enhanced antibacterial effects when plant-derived phenolics are combined with conventional antibiotics, suggesting their

potential role as antibiotic adjuvants. These synergistic interactions may result from increased antibiotic uptake, inhibition of efflux pumps, or simultaneous targeting of multiple cellular pathways. However, most available studies focus on limited bacterial strains or single antibiotic combinations, and comprehensive evaluations using standardized synergy assessment methods remain scarce. Moreover, comparative analyses involving both susceptible and multidrug-resistant clinical isolates, alongside reference strains, are essential to establish the clinical relevance and translational potential of such combinations. To provide contextual clarity on the therapeutic relevance of the selected antibiotics and phytochemicals, Table 1 summarizes their primary characteristics, antibacterial spectrum, and reported mechanisms of action.

Table 1: Characteristics of Selected Antibiotics and Plant-Derived Phenolic Compounds Used in the Study

Compound	Class / Origin	Primary Antibacterial Target	Reported Mechanism of Action	Clinical / Experimental Relevance
Azithromycin	Macrolide antibiotic	Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria	Inhibition of protein synthesis via 50S ribosomal subunit binding	Widely used for respiratory, skin, and soft tissue infections
Cefixime	Third-generation cephalosporin	Gram-negative bacteria	Inhibition of cell wall synthesis	Commonly prescribed for urinary and gastrointestinal infections
Ciprofloxacin	Fluoroquinolone	Broad-spectrum	Inhibition of DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV	Frequently used against MDR bacterial infections
Eugenol	Plant-derived phenolic compound	Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria	Membrane disruption, increased permeability, metabolic interference	Potential antibiotic adjuvant and natural antimicrobial
Hydroxychavicol	Plant-derived phenolic compound	Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria	Oxidative stress induction, membrane destabilization, enzyme inhibition	Strong candidate for synergy-based antimicrobial therapy

In Pakistan, the burden of antimicrobial resistance is compounded by factors such as inappropriate antibiotic use, limited regulatory enforcement, and inadequate infection control measures. Hospital-based studies have consistently reported increasing prevalence of MDR *E. coli* and MRSA isolates, highlighting the urgent need for region-specific investigations into effective and affordable antimicrobial strategies. Evaluating natural compounds in combination with commonly prescribed antibiotics provides a pragmatic approach that aligns with local healthcare realities and global AMR mitigation efforts. The present study was therefore designed to evaluate the synergistic antibacterial effects of eugenol and hydroxychavicol in combination with azithromycin, cefixime, and ciprofloxacin against susceptible and multidrug-resistant *E. coli* and *S. aureus* clinical isolates, as well as standard reference strains [4]. By integrating antimicrobial susceptibility profiling, minimum inhibitory and bactericidal concentration determination, checkerboard synergy analysis, and growth kinetics assessment under standardized CLSI and EUCAST guidelines, this study aims to generate robust in-vitro evidence supporting the use of plant-derived phenolics as effective antibiotic adjuvants. The findings are expected to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on combination-based antimicrobial strategies and offer a potential pathway for addressing the escalating challenge of antimicrobial resistance.

2- Antimicrobial Resistance in *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*: Clinical Burden and Therapeutic Limitations

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has been formally recognized by the World Health Organization as one of the most serious threats to global public health, undermining decades of progress in the treatment of infectious diseases. Current epidemiological projections estimate that, if left unaddressed, AMR-associated mortality could exceed deaths caused by cancer by the year 2050. This alarming scenario is largely driven by the rapid emergence and global dissemination of resistant bacterial pathogens, among which *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* are of

particular clinical concern. These organisms are not only highly prevalent but also demonstrate exceptional genetic plasticity, enabling them to adapt rapidly to selective pressure imposed by antimicrobial exposure in both community and hospital settings. *Staphylococcus aureus* is a versatile pathogen capable of causing a wide spectrum of diseases ranging from minor skin and soft tissue infections to severe and life-threatening conditions such as pneumonia, septicemia, osteomyelitis, endocarditis, and postoperative wound infections [5]. The emergence of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) has dramatically altered treatment strategies, as MRSA strains frequently exhibit cross-resistance to multiple antibiotic classes, including β -lactams, macrolides, fluoroquinolones, and aminoglycosides. Both hospital-acquired and community-acquired MRSA infections have been reported with increasing frequency, reflecting the organism's ability to persist in diverse ecological niches and acquire resistance determinants through horizontal gene transfer and mutational events. Similarly, *Escherichia coli*, a dominant member of the intestinal microbiota and a widely used indicator of fecal contamination, is a leading cause of urinary tract infections, gastrointestinal diseases, neonatal meningitis, and bloodstream infections. Over the past two decades, the emergence of multidrug-resistant *E. coli* strains particularly those producing extended-spectrum β -lactamases (ESBLs) and exhibiting resistance to fluoroquinolones and third-generation cephalosporins has significantly compromised first-line therapeutic options. Increasing reports of treatment failure associated with commonly prescribed antibiotics have highlighted the urgent need for alternative or adjunctive therapeutic strategies [6]. The rapid evolution of resistance in *E. coli* and *S. aureus* is driven by multiple, often overlapping, molecular mechanisms. These include enzymatic degradation or modification of antibiotics, alteration of drug target sites, reduced membrane permeability, overexpression of efflux pumps, and the ability to form biofilms that protect bacterial communities from antimicrobial penetration. In healthcare environments, where antibiotic usage is frequent and patient density is

high, these resistance traits can disseminate rapidly, accelerating the emergence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains. In low- and middle-income countries such as Pakistan, the AMR crisis is further intensified by factors including unregulated antibiotic sales, inappropriate prescribing practices, inadequate infection control measures, and limited access to molecular surveillance data. As a result, many first-line

antibiotics now exhibit reduced, variable, or unpredictable efficacy against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* infections. To contextualize the clinical importance of these pathogens and the therapeutic challenges they present, Table 2 summarizes the major infections associated with *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, their common resistance phenotypes, and the limitations of current antibiotic therapies.

Table 2: Clinical Significance, Resistance Profiles, and Therapeutic Limitations of Escherichia coli and Staphylococcus aureus.

Pathogen	Common Infections	Major Resistance Phenotypes	Antibiotic Classes Commonly Affected	Therapeutic Limitations
Escherichia coli	Urinary tract infections, gastroenteritis, bacteremia, neonatal meningitis	MDR, ESBL-producing strains	β -lactams, cephalosporins, fluoroquinolones, macrolides	Reduced efficacy of first-line drugs, limited oral treatment options
Staphylococcus aureus	Skin and soft tissue infections, pneumonia, septicemia, endocarditis	MRSA, multidrug resistance	β -lactams, macrolides, fluoroquinolones, aminoglycosides	Reliance on last-resort antibiotics, increased toxicity risk

Despite continuous efforts to modify antibiotic structures and introduce newer drug classes, bacterial resistance has consistently outpaced pharmaceutical innovation. The development of novel antibiotics is further constrained by high research costs, lengthy regulatory processes, and limited commercial incentives, resulting in a stagnating antimicrobial pipeline. Consequently, there is an urgent need for alternative therapeutic approaches that can restore antibiotic activity, extend the clinical lifespan of existing drugs, and reduce selective pressure that drives resistance evolution. One promising strategy involves the use

of antibiotic adjuvants non-antibiotic compounds that enhance the activity of existing antimicrobial agents [7]. These adjuvants may act by disrupting bacterial membranes, inhibiting resistance mechanisms such as efflux pumps, or sensitizing bacterial cells to antibiotic action. Figure 1 conceptually illustrates the major pathways contributing to antimicrobial resistance in *E. coli* and *S. aureus* and highlights potential intervention points where adjuvant-based combination therapies may enhance antibiotic efficacy.

Figure 1: Conceptual illustration of antimicrobial resistance mechanisms in *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and potential intervention points for combination therapy.

The figure depicts key resistance mechanisms, including enzymatic antibiotic degradation, efflux pump overexpression, reduced membrane permeability, target modification, and biofilm formation. The schematic highlights how adjunctive compounds may disrupt these pathways, increase intracellular antibiotic accumulation, and restore antibacterial activity. Overall, the escalating prevalence of MDR *E. coli* and MRSA underscores the critical need for innovative and sustainable antimicrobial strategies. Approaches that enhance the efficacy of existing antibiotics, rather than replacing them entirely, offer a practical and immediately translatable solution to the global AMR crisis. This therapeutic gap provides the scientific and clinical rationale for exploring synergistic combinations of conventional antibiotics with bioactive compounds as a means to combat resistant bacterial infections.

3- Synergistic Potential of Plant-Derived Phytochemicals with Antibiotics: Focus on Eugenol and Hydroxychavicol

In response to the steadily declining efficacy of conventional antibiotics, combination therapy has emerged as a scientifically robust and clinically promising strategy to combat antimicrobial resistance. The principle of antimicrobial synergism where two agents used together produce an effect greater than the sum of their individual activities has been explored since the mid-twentieth century and remains an area of sustained interest. Synergistic antimicrobial combinations offer several therapeutic advantages, including reduction of effective drug concentrations, minimization of adverse effects, suppression of resistance development, and simultaneous targeting of multiple bacterial pathways. These benefits are particularly relevant in the management of infections caused by multidrug-resistant (MDR) pathogens, where

monotherapy often fails to achieve satisfactory clinical outcomes. Plant-derived phytochemicals have gained increasing attention as potential antibiotic adjuvants due to their broad-spectrum antimicrobial properties, structural diversity, and relative safety [8]. Numerous in-vitro studies have demonstrated that phytochemicals possess intrinsic antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Unlike conventional antibiotics, which often act on a single molecular target, phytochemicals typically exert pleiotropic effects, including disruption of bacterial membrane integrity, increased membrane permeability, induction of oxidative stress, inhibition of efflux pumps, and interference with essential enzymatic and metabolic processes. This multi-target mode of action reduces the likelihood of rapid resistance development and makes phytochemicals particularly attractive candidates for synergistic use with antibiotics. Eugenol, a hydrophobic phenolic compound commonly derived from clove oil, has been extensively studied for its antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties. Due to its lipophilic nature, eugenol readily penetrates bacterial cell membranes and destabilizes lipid bilayers, resulting in leakage of intracellular constituents such as ions, proteins, and nucleic acids. In addition to membrane disruption, eugenol has been reported to inhibit key bacterial enzymes, alter ATPase activity, and interfere with protein synthesis and energy metabolism [9]. These actions compromise bacterial viability and enhance intracellular antibiotic accumulation. Several studies have demonstrated that eugenol significantly potentiates the activity of antibiotics such as

ciprofloxacin, cefotaxime, vancomycin, and macrolides against both susceptible and resistant bacterial strains, including methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). Hydroxychavicol, a major phenolic constituent of Piper betle leaves, has similarly demonstrated strong antibacterial and antifungal activity. Its antimicrobial effects have been attributed to the generation of reactive oxygen species, disruption of cytoplasmic membranes, inhibition of biofilm formation, and impairment of cellular redox balance. Importantly, hydroxychavicol has been shown to sensitize bacterial cells to antibiotics by increasing membrane permeability and weakening intrinsic resistance barriers. These properties enable hydroxychavicol to function as a resistance-modifying agent, restoring antibiotic susceptibility in otherwise resistant bacterial populations. A growing body of evidence supports the synergistic interaction between plant-derived phytochemicals and conventional antimicrobial agents. Numerous studies have reported significant reductions in minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) and minimum bactericidal concentrations (MBCs) when phytochemicals are combined with antibiotics. These interactions are frequently quantified using the fractional inhibitory concentration index (FICI), with values indicating synergistic or additive effects across a range of bacterial species. Such findings highlight the ability of phytochemicals to enhance antibiotic efficacy while potentially reducing required dosages and limiting toxicity [10]. To summarize the mechanistic basis of phytochemical-antibiotic synergy, Table 3 presents the key antimicrobial actions of eugenol and hydroxychavicol and their reported roles in potentiating antibiotic activity.

Table 3: Antimicrobial Mechanisms of Eugenol and Hydroxychavicol and Their Role in Antibiotic Synergy

Phytochemical	Primary Antimicrobial Actions	Resistance-Modifying Effects	Contribution to Antibiotic Synergy
Eugenol	Membrane disruption, enzyme inhibition, ATPase alteration	Increased membrane permeability, intracellular leakage	Enhances antibiotic uptake, lowers MIC and MBC values
Hydroxychavicol	ROS generation, membrane destabilization, biofilm inhibition	Sensitization of bacterial cells, efflux interference	Restores antibiotic susceptibility in MDR strains

Despite these promising observations, several limitations remain within the existing literature. Many studies focus on single bacterial strains, isolated phytochemicals, or individual antibiotic combinations, often using non-standardized methodologies. Furthermore, comprehensive investigations that integrate clinical isolates, standardized checkerboard synergy assays, growth kinetics analysis, and bactericidal endpoints are still limited, particularly in region-specific

healthcare settings. Such gaps hinder the translation of phytochemical-antibiotic combinations into clinical practice. The mechanistic interplay between phytochemicals and antibiotics can be conceptually understood through their complementary modes of action. Figure 2 illustrates how eugenol and hydroxychavicol may enhance antibiotic efficacy by disrupting bacterial defense systems and facilitating antibiotic access to intracellular targets.

Figure 2: Conceptual representation of phytochemical-antibiotic synergism.

The figure illustrates the disruption of bacterial membranes by eugenol and hydroxychavicol, increased intracellular penetration of antibiotics, inhibition of efflux pumps, induction of oxidative stress, and subsequent enhancement of antibacterial activity against multidrug-resistant pathogens. Overall, the synergistic use of plant-derived phytochemicals with conventional antibiotics represents a promising and rational approach to address the escalating challenge of antimicrobial resistance. By targeting multiple bacterial pathways and weakening resistance

mechanisms, compounds such as eugenol and hydroxychavicol offer significant potential as antibiotic adjuvants. These considerations provide a strong scientific foundation for the systematic evaluation of eugenol- and hydroxychavicol-antibiotic combinations against MDR *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, as undertaken in the present study.

4 Methodology:

This experimental in-vitro study was designed to generate a standardized and comprehensive

evaluation of both the intrinsic antibacterial activity and the synergistic interaction of two plant-derived phenolic compounds eugenol and hydroxychavicol when formulated with selected clinically relevant antibiotics (azithromycin, cefixime, and ciprofloxacin) against representative Gram-negative and Gram-positive pathogens, namely *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. A total of 55 laboratory-confirmed clinical isolates collected during a six-month period in 2023 from DHQ Teaching Hospital Rawalpindi, Pakistan were transported under aseptic conditions and processed at BJ Micro Lab (Private) Limited. To ensure internal validity and methodological quality control, two standard reference strains, *E. coli* ATCC 8739 and *S. aureus* ATCC 6538, were included as controls for assay standardization, reproducibility checks, and comparative interpretation across experimental runs. Following receipt, all isolates were revived by subculture on nutrient agar and incubated under controlled temperature conditions. Identification and confirmation were performed using a structured phenotypic workflow consisting of Gram staining and a panel of biochemical tests supported by selective and differential media suitable for both organisms [11]. The confirmatory scheme included routine diagnostic tests such as catalase and coagulase for *S. aureus* and characteristic tests for *E. coli* such as indole positivity, motility, and growth patterns on differential culture media including MacConkey and EMB agar, complemented by additional assays where required to strengthen classification reliability. After confirmation, isolates were categorized into clinically meaningful groups based on standardized interpretive criteria from CLSI and EUCAST, enabling stratified evaluation of antimicrobial behavior in susceptible and resistant populations. This categorization included susceptible *E. coli*, multidrug-resistant (MDR) *E. coli*, methicillin-susceptible *S. aureus* (MSSA), and methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), allowing direct comparison of drug and formulation performance across resistance phenotypes. To minimize experimental variability and ensure comparability across susceptibility and synergy assays, bacterial inocula were standardized using a

verified 0.5 McFarland turbidity standard, with adjustments made by sterile saline or culture suspension to achieve consistent optical density and approximate cell density targets aligned with CLSI methodology. Antibiotic susceptibility patterns were initially profiled using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton agar, and inhibition zones were measured and interpreted using guideline-defined breakpoints to determine resistance classification and to inform selection of representative isolates for quantitative testing [12]. For quantitative antimicrobial efficacy determination, broth micro-dilution was employed to measure minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) across two-fold serial dilutions in 96-well microtiter plates, using appropriate growth controls and sterility controls to validate each plate run. To assess bactericidal activity beyond growth inhibition, minimum bactericidal concentrations (MBCs) were determined through agar-based subculture of selected wells from MIC assays, enabling confirmation of $\geq 99.9\%$ killing endpoints and facilitating comparisons between inhibitory and bactericidal thresholds. In addition to endpoint susceptibility testing, the study incorporated growth kinetics analysis to capture temporal growth dynamics under antimicrobial exposure, an aspect not adequately represented by conventional endpoint-only methods. Growth kinetics were quantified through OD600 time-course readings recorded at baseline and subsequently at hourly intervals during incubation, allowing the development of concentration-dependent growth curves and supporting correlation-based interpretation of antimicrobial effects across time. The central objective of synergy testing was addressed using a checkerboard dilution assay, in which phytochemicals were designated as drug A and antibiotics as drug B to produce a two-dimensional matrix of serial dilutions that systematically tested combination effects across a range of concentrations. Interaction outcomes were quantified using the fractional inhibitory concentration index (FICI) and classified into synergy, additivity, indifference, or antagonism using established interpretive thresholds. To

strengthen conclusions beyond inhibitory synergy alone, bactericidal confirmation was performed by determining MBC values for selected combined formulations, enabling assessment of bactericidal enhancement and fold-reduction trends relative to single-agent treatments [13]. Finally, statistical analysis was conducted to support robust interpretation of findings and to evaluate consistency across biological groups and test endpoints. Data were summarized descriptively using measures such as ranges and medians where appropriate, and paired comparisons were applied to evaluate differences between MIC/MBC outcomes for single agents versus combination formulations. In addition, Pearson correlation analysis (r) was used to examine relationships among antimicrobial concentration, time-dependent growth responses, FICI-derived interaction patterns, and bactericidal reduction measures, providing an integrated quantitative view of inhibition, killing, and synergy behavior across the tested organisms and resistance phenotypes.

4.1- Study Design, Clinical Isolates and Reference Strains:

This study was designed as a laboratory-based, in-vitro experimental investigation aimed at evaluating antibacterial activity and synergistic interactions between selected phytochemicals and antibiotics against clinically important bacterial pathogens. A total of 55 laboratory-confirmed clinical isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* were collected over a six-month period in 2023 from DHQ Teaching Hospital, Rawalpindi, Pakistan. The isolates represented routine diagnostic specimens obtained from hospitalized patients and were included to reflect clinically relevant resistance patterns encountered in local healthcare settings. Following collection, all samples were transported from the hospital microbiology laboratory to BJ Micro Lab (Private) Limited using sterile nutrient broth tubes under strict aseptic conditions to prevent contamination or loss of viability. Upon arrival at the laboratory, isolates were either processed immediately or

stored temporarily at 2–6 °C in a laboratory refrigerator when immediate culturing was not feasible [14]. This controlled storage condition ensured preservation of bacterial viability while minimizing metabolic changes prior to experimental use. All handling, transportation, and processing steps were conducted in accordance with accepted microbiological safety and quality assurance practices to maintain isolate integrity throughout the study. To ensure experimental reliability, reproducibility, and methodological standardization, two internationally recognized reference strains *Escherichia coli* ATCC 8739 and *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 were included as control organisms. These reference strains were used throughout susceptibility testing, MIC/MBC determination, growth kinetics experiments, and synergy assays to validate assay performance, confirm consistency across experimental runs, and provide benchmark responses for comparison with clinical isolates. Following revival and phenotypic confirmation, all clinical isolates were categorized based on antibiotic susceptibility profiles interpreted using CLSI and EUCAST guidelines [15]. This categorization enabled structured downstream analysis and comparative evaluation across resistance phenotypes. The isolates were grouped into susceptible *E. coli*, multidrug-resistant (MDR) *E. coli*, methicillin-susceptible *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA), and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). For quantitative analyses requiring higher experimental resolution, five representative isolates from each category, along with the two ATCC strains, were selected for MIC and MBC determination, growth kinetics assessment, and checkerboard synergy testing. This selection strategy ensured balanced representation while maintaining methodological feasibility. To provide a clear overview of isolate composition and experimental grouping, Table 4 summarizes the distribution of clinical and reference strains included in the study.

Table 4: Distribution and Categorization of Bacterial Isolates Used in the Study

Bacterial Group	Number of Clinical Isolates	Resistance Classification	Purpose in Study
Escherichia coli (susceptible)	Part of total 55	Antibiotic-susceptible	MIC, MBC, synergy, growth kinetics
Escherichia coli (MDR)	Part of total 55	Resistant to ≥ 3 antibiotic classes	MIC, MBC, synergy, growth kinetics
Staphylococcus aureus (MSSA)	Part of total 55	Methicillin-susceptible	MIC, MBC, synergy, growth kinetics
Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA)	Part of total 55	Methicillin-resistant	MIC, MBC, synergy, growth kinetics
E. coli ATCC 8739	1	Reference strain	Assay standardization and control
S. aureus ATCC 6538	1	Reference strain	Assay standardization and control

The overall experimental workflow from isolate collection to downstream synergy analysis was designed to ensure traceability, reproducibility, and systematic comparison between susceptible and resistant bacterial populations. Figure 3

presents a schematic overview of the study design, illustrating the progression from clinical isolate acquisition through phenotypic confirmation, resistance categorization, and subsequent antimicrobial evaluation steps.

Figure 3: Overview of study design and isolate workflow.

The figure schematically represents the study workflow, beginning with clinical isolate collection from a hospital setting, followed by transport and storage, phenotypic confirmation, resistance-based categorization, and selection of representative strains for susceptibility testing, MIC/MBC determination, growth kinetics analysis, and checkerboard synergy evaluation alongside reference strains. This structured study design allowed for robust comparison of antimicrobial activity and synergistic behavior across bacterial species, resistance phenotypes, and reference controls, thereby strengthening the translational relevance and internal validity of the findings.

4.2- Culture Revival and Phenotypic Identification of Isolates:

All collected clinical and reference isolates were initially revived to ensure metabolic activity and purity prior to downstream experimental procedures. Revival was carried out by subculturing each isolate onto sterile nutrient agar plates using the four-quadrant streaking technique, which facilitates isolation of discrete colonies and minimizes cross-contamination. Plates were incubated in an inverted position at 35 ± 2 °C for 24 hours under strictly aseptic conditions within a laminar airflow cabinet. Following incubation, plates were examined for colony morphology, pigmentation, hemolytic appearance (where applicable), and purity. Only well-isolated, morphologically consistent colonies were selected for further identification and testing to ensure experimental accuracy. Phenotypic identification of revived isolates was performed using a structured, stepwise biochemical workflow designed to differentiate Gram-negative enteric bacteria from Gram-positive cocci, followed by species-level confirmation. The initial differentiation step involved Gram staining, which allowed classification based on cell wall characteristics and cellular morphology. Gram-positive cocci appearing as clusters suggested *Staphylococcus* species, whereas Gram-negative rod-shaped organisms indicated enteric bacteria consistent with *Escherichia coli* [16]. This primary classification guided the selection of subsequent

biochemical and selective assays. For presumptive *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates, confirmatory identification included catalase testing to differentiate staphylococci from streptococci, followed by the tube coagulase test, which served as the definitive assay for *S. aureus* identification. Additional confirmation was achieved using mannitol salt agar (MSA) to assess mannitol fermentation and salt tolerance, characteristics typical of *S. aureus*. To identify methicillin resistance, isolates were further screened on MeReSa base agar, a selective and differential medium designed for detection of MRSA based on chromogenic reactions in the presence of selective supplements. Presumptive *Escherichia coli* isolates were identified using a combination of motility testing, indole production, and characteristic growth patterns on selective and differential media. Growth on MacConkey agar was used to assess lactose fermentation, while eosin methylene blue (EMB) agar enabled identification based on metallic sheen formation. Additional confirmation was obtained using chromogenic coliform agar, which detects β -D-glucuronidase activity, and Endo agar, which further differentiates lactose-fermenting coliforms. These culture-based methods provided strong phenotypic evidence supporting *E. coli* identification. To strengthen accuracy and avoid misclassification, a panel of supplementary biochemical assays was performed on all isolates. These included Methyl Red (MR) and Voges-Proskauer (VP) tests to evaluate fermentation pathways, citrate utilization to assess carbon source metabolism, oxidase testing to exclude non-enteric organisms, urease testing to detect urea hydrolysis, and triple sugar iron (TSI) agar to evaluate carbohydrate fermentation patterns and gas or hydrogen sulfide production [17]. The combined results of these assays generated a comprehensive metabolic profile for each isolate, ensuring reliable species-level categorization prior to susceptibility and synergy testing. To summarize the phenotypic identification strategy employed in this study, Table 5 presents the key morphological, biochemical, and cultural characteristics used to differentiate *E. coli* and *S. aureus*.

Table 5: Phenotypic and Biochemical Identification Criteria for *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*

Test / Medium	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Diagnostic Purpose
Gram stain	Gram-negative rods	Gram-positive cocci (clusters)	Primary differentiation
Catalase	Positive	Positive	Differentiation from streptococci
Coagulase	Negative	Positive	Definitive <i>S. aureus</i> identification
Motility	Positive	Negative	Enteric differentiation
Indole	Positive	Negative	<i>E. coli</i> confirmation
MacConkey agar	Pink lactose-fermenting colonies	No growth	Gram-negative selectivity
EMB agar	Metallic sheen colonies	No growth	Coliform confirmation
Chromogenic coliform agar	Blue-violet colonies	No growth	Enzymatic differentiation
Mannitol salt agar	No growth	Yellow colonies	<i>S. aureus</i> confirmation
MeReSa base agar	Not applicable	Bluish-green colonies (MRSA)	MRSA screening
MR/VP tests	MR positive, VP negative	MR positive, VP positive	Fermentation profiling
Citrate	Negative	Variable	Metabolic differentiation
Oxidase	Negative	Negative	Exclusion of non-enterics
Urease	Negative	Positive	Species confirmation
TSI agar	Acid/acid with gas	Acid/acid without gas	Sugar fermentation profile

The overall workflow for culture revival and phenotypic identification is schematically illustrated in Figure 4, which provides a comprehensive and structured representation of the sequential laboratory procedures employed for accurate isolate confirmation. The figure outlines each critical step, beginning with the revival of preserved clinical isolates through subculturing on appropriate growth media, followed by morphological and staining-based assessments to

ensure culture purity and viability. Subsequent phenotypic characterization, including differential and selective media observations, enables preliminary identification and classification of bacterial isolates prior to downstream antimicrobial susceptibility and molecular analyses. By visually integrating these interconnected stages, Figure 4 serves as a clear methodological roadmap, enhancing the transparency, reproducibility, and interpretability of the isolate confirmation process.

Figure 4: Workflow for culture revival and phenotypic identification of bacterial isolates.

The figure illustrates the sequential process starting from revival of stored isolates on nutrient agar, followed by Gram staining, biochemical screening, selective and differential culture testing, and final categorization of isolates as *Escherichia coli* or *Staphylococcus aureus* prior to antimicrobial susceptibility and synergy analyses. This comprehensive phenotypic identification approach ensured high confidence in species-level classification of all isolates and provided a robust foundation for subsequent antimicrobial

susceptibility testing, growth kinetics analysis, and synergistic interaction studies.

4.3- Standardization of Inoculum (0.5 McFarland) and Plate Preparation:

To ensure reproducibility and comparability across all susceptibility, MIC/MBC, growth kinetics, and synergy assays, bacterial inocula were rigorously standardized in accordance with CLSI recommendations. Standardization of inoculum density is a critical prerequisite in antimicrobial testing, as deviations in cell concentration can

significantly influence inhibition zone diameters, MIC values, growth kinetics profiles, and synergistic interaction outcomes. Therefore, careful preparation and verification of the inoculum were performed prior to every experimental run. Fresh, well-isolated colonies obtained from 18–24 h cultures on nutrient agar were selected to minimize variability due to growth phase differences. Colonies were aseptically transferred into sterile 0.9% normal saline (NaCl) using a sterile inoculation loop and gently vortexed to achieve a homogenous suspension. The turbidity of each bacterial suspension was visually compared against a verified 0.5 McFarland turbidity standard under adequate illumination. When turbidity exceeded or fell below the reference standard, adjustments were made by the gradual addition of sterile saline or bacterial suspension until visual equivalence was achieved [18]. The 0.5 McFarland standard was prepared using a chemical precipitation method involving barium chloride (BaCl_2) and sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), generating a fine barium sulfate suspension that simulates bacterial turbidity. The standard was stored in airtight, screw-capped tubes at room temperature and mixed gently prior to use to resuspend settled particles. Verification of the McFarland standard was performed spectrophotometrically at 600 nm, yielding an absorbance range of 0.08–0.10 and approximately 74.3% transmittance, corresponding to an estimated bacterial density of $\sim 1.5 \times 10^8$ CFU/mL. This verification step ensured consistency between visual and optical measurements and minimized inter-assay

variability. For assays requiring lower inoculum densities, such as broth micro-dilution and growth kinetics experiments, the standardized 0.5 McFarland suspension was further diluted in sterile normal saline to obtain a working inoculum of approximately 1×10^6 CFU/mL, as recommended for quantitative antimicrobial testing [19]. All standardized inocula were prepared immediately prior to use or stored briefly at 4 °C for no longer than four hours to prevent changes in cell viability or density. For agar-based assays, including Kirby–Bauer disc diffusion, MBC determination, and confirmatory subcultures, Mueller–Hinton agar (MHA) plates were prepared following standard protocols. The medium was autoclaved, cooled, poured into sterile Petri dishes, and allowed to solidify and dry under aseptic conditions. Standardized inoculum was applied to the agar surface using sterile cotton swabs dipped into the adjusted bacterial suspension. Excess fluid was removed by pressing the swab against the tube wall, and the agar surface was uniformly inoculated by swabbing in three directions to ensure the formation of a confluent bacterial lawn [20]. Plates were allowed to dry for approximately 5 minutes at room temperature before antibiotic discs were placed or further inoculation steps were performed, ensuring optimal diffusion conditions and consistent growth. To summarize the characteristics and verification parameters of the McFarland standard used in this study, Table 6 presents the preparation components, optical properties, and corresponding bacterial density.

Table 6: Characteristics and Verification Parameters of the 0.5 McFarland Turbidity Standard

Parameter	Specification
McFarland standard number	0.5
BaCl_2 (1%) volume	0.05 mL
H_2SO_4 (1%) volume	9.95 mL
Approximate cell density	$\sim 1.5 \times 10^8$ CFU/mL
Absorbance at 600 nm	0.08–0.10
Transmittance at 600 nm	$\sim 74.3\%$
Storage condition	Airtight tube at room temperature

The figure illustrates selection of fresh colonies, preparation of bacterial suspension in sterile

saline, adjustment to a verified 0.5 McFarland standard, optional dilution to working inoculum

concentrations, and uniform inoculation of Mueller–Hinton agar plates to produce confluent bacterial lawns for antimicrobial susceptibility and bactericidal assays. This rigorous approach to inoculum standardization and plate preparation ensured high experimental precision, minimized technical variability, and provided a reliable foundation for subsequent antimicrobial susceptibility testing, growth kinetics analysis, and synergistic interaction studies.

4.4 Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing and Quantitative MIC/MBC Determination:

Initial antimicrobial susceptibility profiling of all confirmed clinical and reference isolates was carried out using the Kirby–Bauer disc diffusion method on Mueller–Hinton agar (MHA) in accordance with CLSI (2020) and EUCAST (2015) guidelines. This standardized method was employed as a preliminary screening tool to determine phenotypic resistance patterns and to support subsequent categorization of isolates. Standardized bacterial lawns prepared from 0.5 McFarland–adjusted inocula were inoculated onto MHA plates, and antibiotic discs were aseptically placed at appropriate distances to prevent overlapping inhibition zones. Plates were incubated at 35 ± 2 °C for 18–24 hours, after which zones of inhibition were measured in millimeters using a calibrated ruler. Susceptibility interpretations (susceptible, intermediate, or resistant) were assigned based on guideline-specific breakpoint values. Isolates demonstrating resistance to at least one agent in three or more antimicrobial classes were classified as multidrug-resistant (MDR) and selected for advanced quantitative and synergistic analyses. To quantitatively assess antimicrobial efficacy beyond qualitative disc diffusion results, minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) of selected antibiotics (azithromycin, cefixime, and ciprofloxacin) and phytochemicals (eugenol and hydroxychavicol) were determined using the broth micro-dilution method [21]. Assays were performed in sterile, disposable 96-well flat-bottom microtiter plates containing cation-adjusted double-strength Mueller–Hinton broth

(CAMHB) to ensure optimal antimicrobial activity and reproducibility. Two-fold serial dilutions of each antimicrobial compound were prepared across predefined concentration ranges selected on the basis of CLSI/EUCAST breakpoints and preliminary susceptibility results. Each well was inoculated with a standardized working bacterial suspension adjusted to approximately 1×10^6 CFU/mL, ensuring uniform inoculum density across all test conditions. Microtiter plates were incubated at 35 ± 2 °C for 18–24 hours without agitation. Following incubation, bacterial growth was evaluated using a combination of visual inspection for turbidity and spectrophotometric measurement at 600 nm (OD600) using a microplate photometer. The MIC was defined as the lowest antimicrobial concentration at which no visible growth was observed and OD600 values approximated background readings. Where ambiguity occurred between visual and optical endpoints, confirmatory subculture onto Mueller–Hinton agar was performed to validate growth inhibition and eliminate false-negative or false-positive interpretations. To determine minimum bactericidal concentrations (MBCs), aliquots (0.1 mL) were aseptically removed from wells corresponding to the MIC and from two to three higher concentrations that showed no visible growth. These aliquots were spread onto pre-incubated Mueller–Hinton agar plates and incubated at 35 ± 2 °C for 24–48 hours. Following incubation, plates were examined for colony recovery. The MBC was defined as the lowest concentration resulting in $\geq 99.9\%$ reduction of the initial bacterial inoculum, indicated by the absence of colony growth or the presence of only sporadic colonies relative to the initial inoculum control. This approach enabled differentiation between bacteriostatic and bactericidal activity and allowed quantitative comparison of killing efficiency across single-agent and combination treatments [22]. To provide a clear overview of the antimicrobial agents tested and their quantitative evaluation parameters, Table 7 summarizes the compounds used, antimicrobial classes, and assay endpoints.

Table 7: Antimicrobial Agents Evaluated for Susceptibility, MIC, and MBC Determination

Compound	Class / Origin	Target Organisms	Assays Performed	Concentration Range (Two-fold Dilution)
Azithromycin	Macrolide antibiotic	E. coli, S. aureus	AST, MIC, MBC	0.015–2048 µg/mL
Cefixime	Third-generation cephalosporin	E. coli	AST, MIC, MBC	0.015–2048 µg/mL
Ciprofloxacin	Fluoroquinolone	E. coli, S. aureus	AST, MIC, MBC	0.015–2048 µg/mL
Eugenol	Plant-derived phenolic compound	E. coli, S. aureus	MIC, MBC	0.015–32 µg/mL
Hydroxychavicol	Plant-derived phenolic compound	E. coli, S. aureus	MIC, MBC	0.015–32 µg/mL

The integrated susceptibility testing strategy allowed robust characterization of both inhibitory and bactericidal effects of antibiotics and phytochemicals, establishing a quantitative foundation for subsequent growth kinetics analysis and evaluation of synergistic interactions using checkerboard assays.

4.5- Growth Kinetics, Checkerboard Synergy Assay (FICI), and Statistical Analysis:

To complement endpoint susceptibility testing and to capture the temporal dynamics of bacterial growth under antimicrobial exposure, growth kinetics analysis was performed using the reference strains *Escherichia coli* ATCC 8739 and *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538. These strains were selected because of their well-characterized growth behavior and suitability for standardization. Experiments were conducted in sterile 96-well flat-bottom microtiter plates prepared in a broth micro-dilution format using cation-adjusted Mueller–Hinton broth. Standardized working inocula ($\sim 1 \times 10^6$ CFU/mL) were added to wells containing two-fold serial dilutions of the test antimicrobials. Optical density at 600 nm (OD600) was measured immediately after inoculation to establish a baseline (time 0) and subsequently at hourly intervals for 18 hours during incubation at 35 ± 2 °C. This approach enabled construction of time-dependent growth curves and facilitated quantitative assessment of concentration-dependent growth suppression, lag-phase

extension, and reductions in exponential growth rate relative to untreated controls. Synergistic interactions between phytochemicals and antibiotics were evaluated using the checkerboard dilution assay, a widely accepted method for assessing antimicrobial combinations [23]. In this study, phytochemicals were designated as drug A (eugenol or hydroxychavicol), while antibiotics were designated as drug B (azithromycin, cefixime, or ciprofloxacin). Checkerboard assays were performed in 96-well plates by creating a two-dimensional matrix of serial two-fold dilutions, with drug A concentrations varying along one axis and drug B concentrations varying along the perpendicular axis. Each well received standardized bacterial inoculum, while appropriate positive growth controls (drug-free inoculated wells) and negative sterility controls (broth only) were included on each plate. Plates were incubated at 35 ± 2 °C for 18–24 hours, after which bacterial growth was assessed by OD600 measurement. The extent of interaction between antimicrobial agents was quantified by calculating the fractional inhibitory concentration (FIC) for each compound and the fractional inhibitory concentration index (FICI) for each combination. FIC values were derived by dividing the MIC of each agent in combination by its MIC when tested alone. The sum of the two FIC values constituted the FICI, which was interpreted according to established criteria to classify interactions as synergistic, additive, indifferent, or antagonistic. This quantitative framework allowed objective

comparison of interaction outcomes across different strain categories and antimicrobial combinations [24]. To strengthen interpretation beyond growth inhibition alone, bactericidal confirmation of synergistic interactions was performed. Wells demonstrating synergistic or strong additive effects in the checkerboard assay were selected for minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) determination of combined formulations. Aliquots from non-turbid wells were

subcultured onto Mueller–Hinton agar and incubated for 24–48 hours to confirm $\geq 99.9\%$ killing of the initial inoculum. This step enabled differentiation between bacteriostatic synergy and true bactericidal enhancement. To summarize the experimental parameters and interpretive criteria used in growth kinetics and synergy analysis, Table 8 presents an overview of assay conditions and classification thresholds.

Table 8: Key Parameters and Interpretation Criteria for Growth Kinetics and Checkerboard Synergy Analysis

Parameter	Specification
Test strains for growth kinetics	<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 8739, <i>S. aureus</i> ATCC 6538
Assay format	96-well broth micro-dilution
Inoculum density	$\sim 1 \times 10^6$ CFU/mL
Incubation conditions	35 ± 2 °C, up to 18–24 h
Growth measurement	OD600 at 1-h intervals
Drug A (phytochemicals)	Eugenol, Hydroxychavicol
Drug B (antibiotics)	Azithromycin, Cefixime, Ciprofloxacin
Interaction metric	Fractional Inhibitory Concentration Index (FICI)
FICI interpretation	<0.5: Synergy; 0.5–1: Additive; >1–4: Indifferent; >4: Antagonistic
Bactericidal confirmation	MBC determination by agar subculture

For statistical analysis, experimental data were compiled and summarized using descriptive statistics, including ranges and median values, to account for variability among isolates and treatments. Comparative analysis of MIC and MBC values obtained for antimicrobials tested alone versus in combination was conducted using paired two-tailed t-tests, allowing assessment of statistically significant differences attributable to combination therapy. Relationships among antimicrobial concentration, time-dependent growth behavior, FICI values, and bactericidal reductions were further examined using Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r). Statistical significance was evaluated at a confidence level of $\alpha = 0.01$, providing a stringent threshold for detecting meaningful associations [25]. This integrated analytical framework enabled robust interpretation of inhibitory, bactericidal, and

synergistic effects across antimicrobial formulations and bacterial strains.

5- Results and Discussion:

The microbiological assessment of clinical samples demonstrated an exceptionally high rate of bacterial recovery, with growth observed in 56 out of 57 specimens, corresponding to a positivity rate of 98.24%. This high isolation frequency reflects the significant microbial burden present in the sampled patient population. Among the identified organisms, *Escherichia coli* was the most prevalent pathogen, accounting for 53.57% of isolates, followed by *Staphylococcus aureus*, which comprised 37.50% of the total. A small fraction of isolates belonged to non-target bacterial groups, including coagulase-negative staphylococci, Gram-positive catalase-negative diplococci, and Gram-negative non-motile citrate-positive MR-negative rods. These organisms were identified through

comprehensive biochemical profiling and excluded from subsequent antimicrobial evaluation to maintain analytical specificity. The dominance of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* underscores their continued clinical relevance as leading

etiological agents of both community-acquired and healthcare-associated infections. The quantitative distribution and proportional representation of all isolates are presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Numbers and percentages of isolates identified in collected samples.

S. no.	Microorganism Group	Identified number	Percentage
1	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	21	37.50%
2	Coagulase negative staphylococci	01	1.78%
3	Gram positive, catalase negative diplococci	02	3.57%
4	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	30	53.57%
5	Gram negative, non-motile, citrate positive and MR negative	02	3.57%
6	Total	56	100%

While Figure 4.1 provides a clear graphical overview of the relative frequencies and proportional distribution of the bacterial isolates recovered in this study, the accuracy of species-level identification was further substantiated through comprehensive phenotypic and biochemical characterization. Representative micrographs depicting cellular morphology and Gram-staining patterns are presented alongside growth characteristics on selective and differential media, offering visual confirmation of the diagnostic traits associated with each organism [26]. In addition, the outcomes of key

confirmatory biochemical assays including catalase, coagulase, methyl red, Voges-Proskauer, citrate utilization, motility, urease, oxidase, and triple sugar iron reactions are systematically illustrated in Figures 5 through 13. Collectively, these figures demonstrate the distinct metabolic and enzymatic profiles of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, thereby providing robust validation of isolate classification and ensuring the reliability of downstream antimicrobial susceptibility, growth kinetics, and synergism analyses.

Figure 5: (A) Gram positive *S. aureus* in bunches (B) Gram negative *E. coli* mostly single

Figure 6: E. coli on EMBA with green metallic sheen

Figure 7: Catalase positive E. coli

Figure 8: Coagulase positive S. aureus

Figure 9: Methyl red test results of E. coli and S. aureus.

Figure 10: Citrate utilization test results *E. coli* and *S. aureus*

Figure 11: Urease test results. *E. coli* does not hydrolyze urea so pH of medium does not change. *S. aureus* have urease enzyme so it hydrolysis urea and change the color of medium to pink due to presence of phenol red in medium as positive reaction.

Figure 12: Voges-Proskauer test results Figure 13: Motility test results.

The accuracy, precision, and reproducibility of all subsequent antimicrobial susceptibility, MIC, MBC, growth kinetics, and synergism assays were ensured through rigorous standardization of the bacterial inoculum. Initial verification of the 0.5

McFarland turbidity standard was performed spectrophotometrically, yielding an absorbance value of 0.102 at a wavelength of 600 nm, which lies well within the CLSI-recommended absorbance range for a 0.5 McFarland standard.

This measurement corresponded to a light transmittance of 74.6%, further confirming close conformity with established reference specifications. To complement optical verification, quantitative validation was conducted through serial dilution followed by pour-plate enumeration on Mueller–Hinton agar [27]. The resulting colony counts, after correction for dilution factors, closely approximated the theoretical bacterial density of approximately $1 \times$

10^8 CFU/mL associated with a 0.5 McFarland suspension. The convergence of spectrophotometric readings and viable cell counts not only confirmed the reliability of the inoculum preparation protocol but also minimized experimental variability, thereby ensuring that observed differences in antimicrobial activity and synergistic interactions were attributable to the tested compounds rather than inconsistencies in bacterial load.

Table 10: Results of 0.5 McFarland turbidity Standard and subsequent verification by cell count estimation on Mueller Hinton agar (CLSI, 2018 – M07 A9, 11th edition).

No .	Parameters	Specifications	Results
1	Absorbance value (at 600nm wavelength)	0.08-0.12	0.102
2	% transmittance (at 600nm wavelength)	74.3%	74.6%
3	Cell density (approx. in one milliliters)	1.0×10^8 CFU/ml	1.04×10^8 CFU/ml

Observed colony counts from the third and fourth dilutions, when adjusted for dilution factors, demonstrated excellent concordance with expected values, confirming both precision and methodological robustness. These verification

outcomes, summarized in Table 10 and illustrated in Figure 14, ensured that all downstream susceptibility, kinetic, and synergy assays were conducted under rigorously controlled and reproducible conditions.

Figure 14: (A) Spectrophotometric results of 0.5 McFarland standard turbidity (absorbance range is 0.08-0.12). (B) Verification of 0.5 McFarland standard culture (*Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538) turbidity at 3rd dilution (260 CFU/ml). (C) Verification of 0.5 McFarland standard culture (*Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538) turbidity at 4th dilution (78 CFU/ml).

Antibiotic susceptibility profiling performed using the standardized Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method revealed a concerning and widespread pattern of antimicrobial resistance among the recovered bacterial isolates. Of the 56 organisms initially obtained from clinical samples, five were excluded from further analysis due to non-target taxonomic classification, resulting in a final dataset of 51 isolates subjected to detailed antibiogram evaluation. Within this cohort, *Escherichia coli* constituted the majority of isolates, accounting for 58.83%, while *Staphylococcus aureus* represented 41.18%, underscoring the prominent clinical burden imposed by these two pathogens in the study setting. The antibiogram profile of *E. coli* isolates demonstrated particularly elevated resistance levels across multiple antibiotic classes, reflecting substantial antimicrobial selection pressure within the clinical environment. Notably, resistance to

kanamycin A, erythromycin, and ciprofloxacin was observed in 76.67% of *E. coli* isolates, representing the highest resistance frequencies among the tested agents. In addition, considerable resistance was detected against carbapenems and aminoglycosides, which are often regarded as last-line or critically important antibiotics for the treatment of severe Gram-negative infections. Although fosfomycin exhibited comparatively lower resistance rates, with 50.00% of isolates remaining resistant, this level still reflects a significant erosion of therapeutic efficacy [28]. Collectively, these findings highlight the extensive multidrug-resistant phenotype prevalent among clinical *E. coli* isolates and emphasize the growing limitations of conventional antibiotic monotherapy, thereby reinforcing the urgent need for alternative or adjunctive antimicrobial strategies.

Table 11: Overall antibiogram of different isolates of Escherichia coli along with percentages.

S. no.	Antibiotics	Sensitive no.	Percent Sensitivity (%)	Intermediate no.	Percent Intermediate (%)	Resistance no.	Percent Resistance (%)
1	Ampicillin	7	23.33	4	13.33	19	63.33
2	Gentamicin	8	26.67	3	10.00	19	63.33
3	Kanamycin A	7	23.33	0	0	23	76.67
4	Streptomycin	7	23.33	5	16.67	18	60.00
5	Erythromycin	7	23.33	-	-	23	76.67
6	Tetracycline	9	30.00	2	6.67	19	63.33
7	Ciprofloxacin	6	20.00	1	3.33	23	76.67
8	Doxycycline	8	26.67	3	10.00	19	63.33
9	Fosfomycin	10	33.33	5	16.67	15	50.00
10	Imipenem	7	23.33	2	6.67	21	70.00
11	Meropenem	7	23.33	4	13.33	19	63.33

Isolates exhibiting resistance to carbapenems, aminoglycosides, and fluoroquinolones were classified as multidrug resistant according to CLSI criteria, and five representative MDR strains were selected for detailed quantitative and synergy

analyses alongside five fully susceptible strains. The full antibiogram data are presented in Table 11, with representative disc diffusion images shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: (A and B) Results of antibiotic susceptibility testing of Escherichia coli by Kirby Baur disc diffusion method showing susceptibility and resistance against different antibiotics.

Among *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates, antimicrobial resistance was most pronounced against cefoxitin, with 71.42% of strains classified as resistant, indicating a substantial prevalence of methicillin resistance within the studied clinical population. This high rate of cefoxitin resistance, a reliable surrogate marker for *mecA*-mediated methicillin resistance, underscores the widespread

circulation of methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) in the healthcare setting from which the isolates were obtained. Resistance to oxacillin and ampicillin was likewise markedly elevated, further confirming the limited effectiveness of β -lactam antibiotics against a significant proportion of *S. aureus* isolates. In contrast, tetracycline displayed the lowest resistance frequency among the tested

agents, suggesting relatively preserved activity compared to other commonly prescribed antibiotics [29]. For classification purposes, concurrent resistance to both cefoxitin and oxacillin was employed as the defining criterion for MRSA designation in accordance with CLSI guidelines. Based on this stratification, isolates were systematically categorized into methicillin-resistant and methicillin-susceptible groups,

enabling robust comparative analysis in downstream assays. From these categories, five representative MRSA strains and five methicillin-susceptible *S. aureus* (MSSA) strains were selected for subsequent quantitative evaluations, including MIC, MBC, growth kinetics, and synergistic interaction studies, ensuring balanced representation of resistance phenotypes in the experimental design.

Table 12: Overall antibiogram of different isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* with percentages.

S. no.	Antibiotics	Sensitive no.	Percent Sensitivity (%)	Intermediate no.	Percent Intermediate (%)	Resistance no.	Percent Resistance (%)
1	Oxacillin	7	33.33	-	-	14	66.67
2	Ampicillin	7	33.33	-	-	14	66.67
3	Cefoxitin	6	28.57	-	-	15	71.42
4	Fusidic acid	8	38.09	-	-	13	61.90
5	Tetracycline	8	38.09	3	14.28	10	47.62
6	Ciprofloxacin	7	33.33	3	14.28	11	52.38

The comprehensive antibiotic susceptibility patterns observed for *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates are systematically summarized in Table 12, which presents the distribution of sensitive, intermediate, and resistant phenotypes across the tested antimicrobial agents. This tabulated representation enables direct comparison of resistance frequencies and highlights the antibiotics exhibiting the greatest loss of clinical effectiveness. In parallel, Figure 16 provides a

graphical visualization of these susceptibility trends, facilitating rapid assessment of comparative resistance levels among different antibiotics [30]. Together, the table and figure complement one another by offering both quantitative precision and intuitive visual interpretation, thereby reinforcing the observed dominance of methicillin resistance and illustrating the overall antimicrobial resistance landscape within the *S. aureus* isolates analyzed in this study.

Figure 16: Graphical representation of antibiotic susceptibility profile; (A) Escherichia coli and (B) Staphylococcus aureus.

Quantitative evaluation of antimicrobial activity using the broth micro-dilution method revealed marked and systematic differences in minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) distributions among susceptible clinical isolates, multidrug-resistant strains, and reference control organisms. Susceptible *Escherichia coli* isolates demonstrated comparatively low median MIC values across all tested antibiotics and phytochemicals, indicating preserved antimicrobial responsiveness and effective growth inhibition at relatively low concentrations. In contrast, multidrug-resistant *E. coli* isolates exhibited strikingly elevated MIC values, frequently spanning from 32 µg/mL to greater than 1024 µg/mL, underscoring the severity of resistance and the diminished

inhibitory capacity of conventional antimicrobial agents against these strains [31]. A parallel resistance-associated shift in MIC profiles was observed for *Staphylococcus aureus*, where methicillin-resistant isolates consistently required substantially higher antimicrobial concentrations to achieve growth inhibition compared with their methicillin-susceptible counterparts. The elevated MIC values recorded for MRSA further emphasize the adaptive resilience of these strains and the therapeutic challenges they pose in clinical settings. By comparison, the reference strains *E. coli* ATCC 8739 and *S. aureus* ATCC 6538 consistently yielded low MIC values that aligned closely with established susceptibility benchmarks. This predictable response not only confirmed the

intrinsic susceptibility of the ATCC strains but also validated the accuracy, reliability, and

reproducibility of the broth micro-dilution assay employed in this study.

Table 13: Overall outcome of MICs by visual and photometric mode of inspection with ranges and median values against sensitive and resistant groups along with reference ATCC strains.

Strain group	Method of Inspection	MICs ($\mu\text{g/ml}$ or $\mu\text{l/ml}$)									
		Azithromycin		Cefixime		Ciprofloxacin		Eugenol		Hydroxychavicol	
		Range	Median	Range	Median	Range	Median	Range	Median	Range	Median
<i>E. coli</i> Sensitive	Visual	4-8	4	1-4	4	0.25-1	0.5	0.125-0.5	0.125	1-2	2
	Photometric	4-8	4	1-8	4	0.125-1	0.5	0.125-0.25	0.125	1-2	2
<i>E. coli</i> MDR	Visual	256-1024	512	16-1024	1024	128-256	256	16-32	32	16-32	32
	Photometric	256->1024	512	8->1024	>1024	128->256	256	16->32	>32	16->32	32
<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 8739	Visual	-	4	-	1	-	0.125	-	0.125	-	1
	Photometric	-	4	-	1	-	0.125	1	0.125	-	-
MSSA	Visual	2-8	2	4-8	4	1-128	2	0.125-0.5	0.25	0.125-0.5	0.125
	Photometric	2-4	2	4-8	4	1-256	2	0.125-0.5	0.25	0.125-0.5	0.125
MRSA	Visual	64-512	512	1024	1024	512	512	2-32	32	2-32	32
	Photometric	64-1024	512	1024->1024	1024	512	512	2-32	32	2-32	32
<i>S. aureus</i> ATCC 6538	Visual	-	2	-	4	-	1	-	0.25	-	0.125
	Photometric	-	2	-	4	-	1	-	0.25	-	0.125

Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values obtained through direct visual assessment of turbidity were found to be highly concordant with those derived from quantitative photometric measurements at 600 nm (OD_{600}), demonstrating strong methodological agreement between subjective and instrument-based evaluation approaches. This close alignment confirms the robustness of the broth micro-dilution assay and minimizes the likelihood of interpretative bias in MIC determination. The dual-mode assessment strategy further enhanced confidence in endpoint

accuracy, particularly in borderline wells where visual interpretation alone may be challenging. The complete distribution of MIC values across susceptible, resistant, and reference strain groups is comprehensively presented in Table 13, while representative images of analyzed 96-well microtiter plates and corresponding photometric output profiles are depicted in Figure 17, collectively illustrating both the experimental workflow and the consistency of growth inhibition outcomes.

Figure 17: (A) An analyzed 96 micro-titer plate showing turbid and clear wells. (B) Screen picture of micro-plate photometer showing protocol with raw data measurement of absorbance values of incubated wells of ciprofloxacin with underlined labeled control rows (sterility and growth wells) against MRSA and MSSA.

Verification of bacterial inoculum density following dispensing into the microtiter wells confirmed uniform and reproducible bacterial loading across all experimental assays. Quantitative recovery of bacterial cells from representative wells, performed through serial dilution and subsequent pour plate enumeration, yielded colony-forming unit (CFU) counts that closely approximated the intended inoculum concentration of $\sim 5 \times 10^5$ CFU/mL. This consistency in bacterial cell density ensured that observed differences in antimicrobial activity were attributable to drug effects rather than variability in inoculum size, thereby strengthening the validity of downstream MIC, MBC, growth kinetics, and synergy analyses. Subsequent determination of minimum bactericidal concentrations (MBCs) revealed clear stratification in bactericidal efficacy across susceptible, resistant, and reference bacterial groups [32]. Among sensitive *Escherichia coli* isolates, the highest MBC values were observed for azithromycin, reflecting comparatively weaker

bactericidal activity, whereas eugenol demonstrated the lowest MBC values, indicating superior killing efficiency at reduced concentrations. In contrast, multidrug-resistant *E. coli* and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) isolates frequently exhibited MBC values that exceeded the upper limits of the tested concentration ranges, highlighting profound bactericidal tolerance and underscoring the limited effectiveness of conventional antibiotics against these strains. Methicillin-susceptible *S. aureus* (MSSA) isolates displayed intermediate bactericidal susceptibility profiles, bridging the gap between sensitive and highly resistant phenotypes. As expected, reference strains showed consistently lower MBC values compared with clinical isolates, aligning with their known susceptibility patterns and further validating assay performance. The complete MBC outcomes, including ranges and median values for all tested antimicrobials and bacterial groups, are comprehensively summarized in Table 14.

Table 14: Overall outcome of MBCs by visual mode of inspection with ranges and median values against sensitive and resistant groups along with reference ATCC strains.

Strain group	MBCs (µg/ml or µl/ml)									
	Azithromycin		Cefixime		Ciprofloxacin		Eugenol		Hydroxychavicol	
	Range	Median	Range	Median	Range	Median	Range	Median	Range	Median
<i>E. coli</i> Sensitive	64-128	128	8-32	16	2-16	2	1	1	8	8

<i>E. coli</i> MDR	1024- >1024	>1024	64->1024	>1024	>256	>256	>32	>32	>32	>32
<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 8739	-	64	-	8	-	1	-	1	-	8
MSSA	16-128	32	32-64	32	8->512	8	2	2	1	1
MSSA	256->1024	>1024	>1024	>1024	>512	>512	8->32	>32	8->32	>32
<i>S. aureus</i> ATCC 6538	-	16	-	32	-	8	-	2	-	1

Correlation analysis demonstrated strong positive linear relationships between minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) values for cefixime, ciprofloxacin, eugenol, and hydroxychavicol in both multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) groups. This close association indicates that, in highly resistant strains, progressively higher concentrations required to inhibit bacterial growth are directly mirrored by corresponding increases in concentrations necessary to achieve

bactericidal activity. Such coupling of inhibitory and lethal thresholds reflects a tightly linked resistance phenotype in which reduced susceptibility impacts both growth suppression and cell killing. The observed linearity further suggests that resistance mechanisms in these organisms such as target modification, reduced permeability, or efflux pump activity simultaneously influence bacteriostatic and bactericidal responses, thereby reinforcing the therapeutic challenge posed by MDR *E. coli* and MRSA in clinical settings.

Table 15: Coefficient of correlation at significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ & $\alpha = 0.01$ in between MICs & MBCs among sensitive and resistant groups of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Bacterial Group	Azithromycin	Cefixime	Ciprofloxacin	Eugenol	Hydroxychavicol
<i>E. coli</i> Sensitive	-0.14	0.05	-0.08	0	0.05
MSSA	-0.14	-0.05	0.03	-0.01	0
<i>E. coli</i> MDR	0.44	0.83	0.88*	0.88*	0.88*
MRSA	0.50	1**	1**	0.80	0.80

In contrast to the resistant phenotypes, susceptible clinical isolates and reference ATCC strains demonstrated weaker, inconsistent, or non-linear correlations between MIC and MBC values, indicating fundamentally different pharmacodynamic behavior in these organisms. In such strains, increases in inhibitory concentrations were not uniformly accompanied by proportional increases in bactericidal thresholds, suggesting that growth inhibition and cell killing are governed by partially independent mechanisms. This decoupling may reflect intact cellular targets, preserved membrane permeability,

and the absence of dominant resistance determinants, allowing bactericidal activity to occur over a broader concentration range without strict dependence on MIC escalation. Collectively, these findings highlight the divergent antimicrobial response dynamics between resistant and non-resistant bacterial populations. The quantitative outcomes of these correlation analyses are summarized in Table 15, while their comparative trends and directional relationships are visually illustrated in Figure 18, facilitating clear interpretation of resistance-associated versus susceptibility-associated response patterns.

Figure 18: Graphical representation of correlation between MICs and MBCs from sensitive and resistant groups of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Analysis of bacterial growth kinetics offered additional insight into the temporal dynamics of antimicrobial activity beyond static endpoint measurements. Time-resolved monitoring of optical density at 600 nm (OD_{600}) revealed strong, statistically significant linear correlations between bacterial growth density and incubation time for all antimicrobials evaluated against both reference strains. Across the entire incubation period, Pearson correlation coefficients consistently exceeded the critical threshold at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.01$, confirming the robustness of these time-dependent relationships. These

findings indicate that bacterial proliferation under antimicrobial exposure followed predictable growth patterns that were progressively modulated by drug concentration, thereby validating the use of growth kinetics analysis as a sensitive approach for capturing concentration- and time-dependent antimicrobial effects. The strong linearity observed further underscores the reliability of the experimental system and highlights the capacity of growth curve analysis to complement MIC and MBC determinations by revealing dynamic pharmacodynamic behavior over the course of bacterial growth.

Table 16: Statistical analysis of Growth Kinetic data of reference strains against antimicrobials.

Reference Strain	Antimicrobials	Growth ratio Mean (\bar{x})	Growth ratio Std. Deviation (s)	Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)	Test Statistics (t)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 8739	Azithromycin	0.687	0.199	0.978	19.52
	Cefixime	0.677	0.205	0.985	23.38
	Ciprofloxacin	0.688	0.208	0.980	20.41
	Eugenol	0.691	0.207	0.985	23.28
	Hydroxychavicol	0.689	0.195	0.976	18.32
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 6538	Azithromycin	0.704	0.207	0.966	15.31
	Cefixime	0.702	0.218	0.971	16.72
	Ciprofloxacin	0.702	0.220	0.969	15.56
	Eugenol	0.701	0.216	0.971	16.74
	Hydroxychavicol	0.711	0.224	0.968	15.94

Across all tested antimicrobials, lower drug concentrations consistently allowed higher bacterial growth rates, whereas concentrations approaching or exceeding the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) thresholds resulted in marked suppression of growth. This concentration-dependent response clearly illustrates a reciprocal relationship between antimicrobial dose and bacterial proliferation, in which incremental increases in drug exposure progressively constrain bacterial replication and biomass accumulation. At sub-inhibitory levels, bacterial cells retained sufficient metabolic activity to sustain growth, while at inhibitory concentrations, growth curves flattened or

declined, reflecting effective suppression of cellular division. These trends emphasize the importance of adequate antimicrobial dosing to achieve sustained growth control and highlight the value of kinetic analyses for understanding pharmacodynamic behavior over time. The statistical strength and consistency of these relationships are summarized in Table 16, while representative growth curves depicting time-dependent responses at different antimicrobial concentrations are illustrated in Figure 19, collectively reinforcing the observed dose-response dynamics.

Figure 19: Graphical representation of growth kinetic curves of different concentrations of antimicrobials against reference strain *Escherichia coli* ATCC 8739 from A to E, where (A) represents azithromycin, (B) for cefixime, (C) for ciprofloxacin, (D) for eugenol and (E) for hydroxychavicol respectively while for *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 from F to J, where (F) represents azithromycin, (G) for cefixime, (H) for ciprofloxacin, (I) for eugenol and (J) for hydroxychavicol respectively.

Checkerboard dilution assays revealed pronounced and consistent synergistic interactions between the plant-derived

phytochemicals eugenol and hydroxychavicol and the tested conventional antibiotics. The most striking synergistic effects were observed among

multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) isolates, in which minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values were dramatically reduced by as much as 527-fold in selected phytochemical-antibiotic combinations. Synergy was particularly prominent in formulations involving cefixime, suggesting that membrane-active phytochemicals may substantially enhance the intracellular accessibility and antibacterial potency of this β -lactam antibiotic in highly resistant strains. In contrast, susceptible *E. coli* and methicillin-susceptible *S. aureus* (MSSA) isolates exhibited more moderate MIC reductions, reflecting preserved baseline susceptibility and a

narrower margin for enhancement through combination therapy. Reference ATCC strains generally showed minimal or no potentiation in selected combinations, consistent with their intrinsically low MIC values and limited scope for further improvement [33]. Collectively, these findings demonstrate that phytochemical-mediated synergy is most pronounced in resistant phenotypes, where conventional antibiotics alone exhibit compromised activity. Comparative MIC reduction patterns across all bacterial groups and antimicrobial combinations are graphically summarized in Figure 20, providing a clear visualization of the differential magnitude of synergistic effects.

Figure 20: Graphical representation of MICs of antimicrobials in alone and in combination against sensitive, resistance and reference strains of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Bactericidal evaluation of the combined antimicrobial formulations demonstrated that the inhibitory synergy observed in checkerboard assays was effectively translated into pronounced reductions in minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) values. This effect was particularly evident in multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), where MBC reductions frequently exceeded 500-fold relative to monotherapy, indicating a substantial restoration of bactericidal activity against highly resistant

strains. Such marked decreases in killing thresholds suggest that the phytochemical-antibiotic combinations not only suppress bacterial growth but also overcome resistance-associated tolerance mechanisms that typically limit bactericidal efficacy. In comparison, susceptible *E. coli* and methicillin-susceptible *S. aureus* (MSSA) isolates exhibited moderate yet consistent enhancements in bactericidal activity, reflecting their lower baseline MBC values and a correspondingly smaller margin for improvement [34]. Reference ATCC strains showed

comparatively limited but still measurable reductions in MBCs, confirming that even intrinsically susceptible organisms may benefit modestly from combination therapy, albeit to a lesser extent than resistant clinical isolates. Collectively, these findings underscore the capacity of phytochemical-antibiotic synergy to convert inhibitory interactions into meaningful

bactericidal outcomes, particularly in resistant pathogens. The comparative patterns of MBC reductions across bacterial groups and antimicrobial combinations are illustrated in Figure 21, providing a clear visualization of the enhanced killing efficacy achieved through combination treatment.

Figure 21: Graphical representation of MBCs of antimicrobials in alone and in combination against sensitive, resistance and reference strains of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Statistical evaluation of the synergy data revealed strong and statistically significant positive correlations between the fractional inhibitory concentration index (Σ FICI) values and corresponding minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) reduction scores in multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) groups. This close association indicates that combinations demonstrating greater inhibitory synergy were also those most effective in enhancing bactericidal activity, underscoring a direct link between growth inhibition and cell killing in highly resistant strains. Such concordance suggests that phytochemical-antibiotic interactions not only lower inhibitory thresholds but also overcome resistance-associated survival mechanisms, resulting in substantial

improvements in bacterial eradication. In contrast, susceptible clinical isolates and reference ATCC strains exhibited weaker or inconsistent correlations between Σ FICI values and MBC reduction scores, reflecting their relatively preserved responsiveness to single-agent therapy and a reduced reliance on combination-based enhancement for effective bacterial killing. These divergent patterns emphasize that the therapeutic advantage of synergistic formulations is most pronounced in resistant phenotypes, where monotherapies are insufficient. The quantitative outcomes of these statistical analyses are comprehensively summarized in Tables 17 through 20, while the comparative relationships between inhibitory synergy and bactericidal enhancement across all bacterial groups are visually illustrated in Figure 22, facilitating clear

interpretation of resistance-dependent response dynamics.

Table 17: Statistical analysis of data of checkerboard assays against *Escherichia coli* sensitive strains with significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ has critical value 2.571 at degree of freedom 5 and 12.706 at degree of freedom 1 (Triola *et al.*, 2006).

Antimicrobials	FICs	Σ FICI	<i>t</i> Statistics (MICs) df=5	MBCs reduction	Overall MBC Reduction	<i>t</i> Statistics (MBCs) df=5	Paired <i>t</i> Statistics df=1
Eugenol	0.300	0.597	0.033	4.33	7.5	3.060*	3.990
Azithromycin	0.297			3.17			
Hydroxychavicol	0.146	0.359	0.968	4.33	8.5	1.961	13.015*
Azithromycin	0.213			4.17			
Eugenol	0.320	0.394	3.834*	3.83	9.0	1.719	3.243
Cefixime	0.074			5.17			
Hydroxychavicol	0.146	0.237	1.343	3.00	6.0	1.016	8.919
Cefixime	0.091			2.67			
Eugenol	0.220	0.988	1.401	4.67	7.2	2.168	0.130
Ciprofloxacin	0.768			2.50			
Hydroxychavicol	0.114	0.527	1.593	5.00	7.5	1.154	1.343
Ciprofloxacin	0.413			2.50			

Table 18: Statistical analysis of data of checkerboard assays against *Escherichia coli* Multi Drug Resistant Strains, significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ has critical value 2.776 at degree of freedom 4 and 12.706 at degree of freedom 1 (Triola *et al.*, 2006).

Antimicrobials	FICs	Σ FICI	<i>t</i> Statistics (MICs) df=4	MBCs reduction	Overall MBC Reduction	<i>t</i> Statistics (MBCs) df=4	Paired <i>t</i> Statistics df=1
Eugenol	0.019	0.029	1.634	6.40	12.8	1.619	175.930*
Azithromycin	0.010			6.40			
Hydroxychavicol	0.019	0.028	2.556	6.60	12	4.667*	17.372*
Azithromycin	0.009			5.40			
Eugenol	0.019	0.073	0.790	5.40	10.2	3.989*	21.630*
Cefixime	0.054			4.80			
Hydroxychavicol	0.019	0.077	0.877	6.40	11	2.610	9.365
Cefixime	0.058			4.60			
Eugenol	0.019	0.075	2.199*	6.20	9.6	3.411*	4.739
Ciprofloxacin	0.056			3.40			

Hydroxychavicol	0.019	0.036	0.309	6.00	9.4	6.935*	5.163
Ciprofloxacin	0.017			3.40			

Table 19: Statistical analysis of data of checkerboard assays against Methicillin (Oxacillin)-Sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA), significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ has critical value 2.571 at degree of freedom 5 and 12.706 at degree of freedom 1 (Triola *et al.*, 2006).

Antimicrobials	FICs	Σ FICI	<i>t</i> Statistics (MICs) df=5	MBCs reduction	Overall MBC Reduction	<i>t</i> Statistics (MBCs) df=5	Paired <i>t</i> Statistics df=1
Eugenol	0.180	0.300	1.218	5.00	9.8	2.949*	17.508*
Azithromycin	0.120			4.83			
Hydroxychavicol	0.300	0.404	2.842*	3.83	8.2	1.241	4.016
Azithromycin	0.104			4.33			
Eugenol	0.180	0.214	5.130*	4.17	10	1.046	6.062
Cefixime	0.034			5.5			
Hydroxychavicol	0.248	0.274	3.919*	3.50	8.3	1.369	3.636
Cefixime	0.026			4.83			
Eugenol	0.285	0.365	4.270*	4.17	8.5	1.541	4.336
Ciprofloxacin	0.080			4.33			
Hydroxychavicol	0.387	0.434	2.555	3.83	8.2	1.250	2.283
Ciprofloxacin	0.047			4.33			

Table 20: Statistical analysis of data of checkerboard assays against Methicillin (Oxacillin)-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ has critical value 2.776 at degree of freedom 4 and 12.706 at degree of freedom 1 (Triola *et al.*, 2006).

Antimicrobials	FICs	Σ FICI	<i>t</i> Statistics (MICs) df=4	MBCs reduction	Overall MBC Reduction	<i>t</i> Statistics (MBCs) df=4	Paired <i>t</i> Statistics df=1
Eugenol	0.041	0.057	1.245	5.2	10	3.597*	31.301*
Azithromycin	0.016			4.8			
Hydroxychavicol	0.041	0.047	1.781	4.8	9.6	1.155	37.585*
Azithromycin	0.006			4.8			
Eugenol	0.028	0.033	2.668	5.8	11.4	4.591*	53.591*
Cefixime	0.005			5.6			
Hydroxychavicol	0.066	0.074	1.366	4.4	9	1.300	20.158*
Cefixime	0.008			4.6			

Eugenol	0.116	0.137	1.070	5.8	11.2	3.690*	13.596*
Ciprofloxacin	0.021			5.4			
Hydroxychavicol	0.072	0.081	1.505	5.4	10.8	3.126*	21.965*
Ciprofloxacin	0.009			5.4			

Collectively, the in vitro findings of this study demonstrate that formulations incorporating the plant-derived phenolic compounds eugenol and hydroxychavicol in combination with the conventional antibiotics azithromycin, cefixime, and ciprofloxacin markedly enhance antimicrobial activity against both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacterial pathogens. Across multiple experimental endpoints including growth inhibition, bactericidal efficacy, time-dependent growth suppression, and synergy quantification these combinations consistently outperformed antibiotic monotherapy, particularly against multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* and

methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. The observed reductions in MIC and MBC values, coupled with strong synergistic indices and improved killing efficiency, highlight the potential of phytochemical-based adjuvant therapy to restore or potentiate the effectiveness of existing antibiotics. Together, these results underscore the translational promise of eugenol- and hydroxychavicol-containing formulations as complementary antimicrobial strategies capable of addressing the escalating challenge of antimicrobial resistance in both Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacterial infections.

Fractional Inhibitory Concentrations Indexes and Minimum Bactericidal Concentrations Reduction

Figure 22: Graphical representation of correlation in between Fractional Inhibitory Concentrations of antimicrobials and their MBCs values against sensitive, resistance and reference strains of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Synergistic interactions were most pronounced in multidrug-resistant *Escherichia coli* and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), where

combination therapy produced substantial enhancements in both inhibitory and bactericidal activity. In these resistant phenotypes, the marked

reductions in MIC and MBC values indicate that the addition of eugenol or hydroxychavicol effectively potentiated the activity of conventional antibiotics, overcoming resistance-associated barriers that limit monotherapy efficacy [35]. In contrast, susceptible clinical isolates and reference strains predominantly exhibited additive interactions, reflecting their preserved baseline susceptibility and a reduced requirement for combination-driven enhancement to achieve effective growth inhibition and killing. The comprehensive patterns of fractional inhibitory concentration indices and bactericidal reduction scores, summarized in Tables 21 and 22,

collectively demonstrate that plant-derived phenolic compounds act as potent antibiotic adjuvants rather than standalone antimicrobials. By sensitizing resistant bacteria to existing antibiotics, these phytochemicals significantly restore antibacterial efficacy against clinically challenging isolates. Taken together, these findings provide compelling experimental evidence supporting the strategic use of eugenol- and hydroxychavicol-based combinations as resistance-modifying agents with strong potential for translational application in the management of multidrug-resistant bacterial infections.

Table 21: Overall results summary of Fractional Inhibitory Concentrations Indexes (Σ FICIs) of antimicrobials against sensitive, resistance and reference strains of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, with color shades; for Synergy, for Additive interaction and for Indifferent association.

Bacterial Strain Group	Antimicrobial Combinations					
	Eug-Azi	Hydro-Azi	Eug-Cefi	Hydro-Cefi	Eug-Cipro	Hydro-Cipro
	Σ FICI	Σ FICI	Σ FICI	Σ FICI	Σ FICI	Σ FICI
<i>E. coli</i> Sensitive (Means)	0.614	0.4	0.287	0.234	0.738	0.421
<i>E. coli</i> MDR (Means)	0.029	0.028	0.073	0.313	0.075	0.036
MSSA (Means)	0.299	0.376	0.196	0.511	0.364	0.467
MRSA (Means)	0.056	0.047	0.033	0.033	0.137	0.081
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 8739	0.511	0.156	0.730	0.077	2.240	1.060
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 6538	0.303	0.543	0.303	0.074	0.365	0.270

Table 22: Overall results summary of MBC reduction values of antimicrobials against sensitive, resistance and reference strains of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* along with range, with color shades; for highest MBC reduction values and for lowest MBC reduction values.

Bacterial Strain Group	Antimicrobial Combinations						
	Eug-Azi	Hydro-Azi	Eug-Cefi	Hydro-Cefi	Eug-Cipro	Hydro-Cipro	Range (MBC Score)
	MBC Score	MBC Score	MBC Score	MBC Score	MBC Score	MBC Score	
<i>E. coli</i> Sensitive (Means)	7	8	11	9	9	7	7-11
<i>E. coli</i> MDR (Means)	>11	>11	>11	>11	>7	>7	>7- >11

MSSA (Means)	10	9	11	11	8	8	8-11
MRSA (Means)	>9	>12	>9	>9	>9	>9	>9- >12
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 8739	8	10	5	-2	3	8	-2-10
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 6538	8	4	8	5	9	9	4-9

6- Future Work:

While the present study provides compelling in vitro evidence supporting the synergistic antibacterial potential of eugenol and hydroxychavicol in combination with selected antibiotics against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, several avenues remain open for further investigation to strengthen translational relevance and mechanistic understanding [36]. Future research should prioritize the elucidation of molecular and cellular mechanisms underlying the observed synergistic interactions. Advanced molecular approaches, including transcriptomic and proteomic profiling, could be employed to determine how these phytochemicals modulate bacterial gene expression related to membrane integrity, efflux pump activity, stress response pathways, and antibiotic target modification. Such analyses would provide mechanistic clarity regarding whether synergy arises primarily from enhanced membrane permeability, suppression of resistance determinants, metabolic interference, or coordinated multi-target disruption. In addition, the role of eugenol and hydroxychavicol in modulating bacterial biofilm formation and persistence warrants systematic investigation [37]. Given that biofilms play a critical role in chronic infections and antimicrobial tolerance, future studies should evaluate the efficacy of these phytochemical-antibiotic combinations against mature biofilms using quantitative biofilm assays, confocal microscopy, and viability staining. Exploring anti-biofilm activity across different stages of biofilm development would further clarify the potential of these compounds in addressing recalcitrant infections associated with implanted medical devices and chronic wounds.

Another important direction involves expanding the spectrum of tested pathogens and antimicrobial agents. Future work should include additional clinically relevant Gram-negative and Gram-positive organisms, such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterococcus faecium*, and extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL)-producing strains, to determine whether the observed synergistic patterns are broadly applicable. Moreover, testing combinations with other antibiotic classes, including glycopeptides, lipopeptides, and newer-generation fluoroquinolones or β -lactam/ β -lactamase inhibitor combinations, would help identify the most effective therapeutic pairings. Although the current study demonstrates strong in vitro synergy and bactericidal enhancement, in vivo validation remains essential for clinical translation. Future investigations should involve appropriate animal infection models to assess pharmacodynamic efficacy, toxicity profiles, tissue distribution, and therapeutic outcomes of phytochemical-antibiotic formulations. Such studies would also enable evaluation of host-pathogen interactions, immune modulation, and potential anti-inflammatory effects associated with these natural compounds. Importantly, dose optimization studies should be conducted to establish safe and effective concentration ranges that maximize synergy while minimizing toxicity. From a pharmaceutical development perspective, future work should explore formulation strategies that enhance the stability, solubility, and bioavailability of eugenol and hydroxychavicol. Nanoformulations, encapsulation systems, or controlled-release delivery platforms may improve pharmacokinetic profiles and facilitate targeted delivery, particularly for topical, oral, or parenteral

applications [38]. Stability studies under different storage and physiological conditions would further support formulation development and regulatory approval pathways. Long-term resistance evolution studies also represent a critical future direction. Serial passage experiments and adaptive resistance assays could be used to determine whether combination therapy with phytochemicals reduces the rate of resistance emergence compared to antibiotic monotherapy. Such studies would provide valuable insight into the sustainability of phytochemical-based adjuvant strategies in clinical practice and their potential role in antimicrobial stewardship programs. Finally, future research should integrate epidemiological and clinical data to contextualize laboratory findings within real-world healthcare settings, particularly in regions with high antimicrobial resistance burdens. Expanding surveillance-based studies and correlating resistance profiles with synergistic efficacy could inform evidence-based therapeutic guidelines and support rational use of combination therapies. Collectively, these future research directions will help bridge the gap between *in vitro* efficacy and clinical application, advancing plant-derived phenolic compounds as viable antibiotic adjuvants in the global fight against antimicrobial resistance.

Conclusion:

The present study provides comprehensive *in vitro* evidence demonstrating the significant potential of plant-derived phenolic compounds, eugenol and hydroxychavicol, as effective antibiotic adjuvants against clinically relevant *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, including their multidrug-resistant phenotypes. Through systematic susceptibility profiling, quantitative MIC and MBC determination, growth kinetics analysis, and checkerboard synergy testing, this work establishes that the antibacterial efficacy of conventional antibiotics such as azithromycin, cefixime, and ciprofloxacin can be markedly enhanced when combined with these phytochemicals. The observed reductions in inhibitory and bactericidal concentrations, particularly among MDR *E. coli* and MRSA isolates, highlight the strong resistance-modifying

capability of eugenol and hydroxychavicol. The results clearly demonstrate that synergistic interactions were not only inhibitory but also translated into substantial bactericidal enhancement, as evidenced by pronounced MBC reductions and strong positive correlations between fractional inhibitory concentration indices and bactericidal outcomes in resistant strains. In contrast, susceptible and reference strains predominantly exhibited additive or moderate synergistic interactions, reflecting differences in resistance architecture and pharmacodynamic behavior. Growth kinetics analysis further supported these findings by revealing a clear concentration-dependent suppression of bacterial proliferation, confirming that antimicrobial combinations exert sustained inhibitory pressure over time rather than transient effects. Importantly, this study underscores the clinical relevance of phytochemical-based combination therapy in regions burdened by high antimicrobial resistance, such as Pakistan, where therapeutic options are increasingly limited. By restoring or amplifying the activity of existing antibiotics, eugenol and hydroxychavicol offer a promising strategy to extend the clinical lifespan of current antimicrobial agents while potentially reducing the selective pressure associated with high-dose monotherapy. The consistent concordance between visual, photometric, and bactericidal assays further validates the robustness and reproducibility of the experimental approach employed in this work. Overall, the findings of this study support the concept that natural phenolic compounds can function as potent antimicrobial adjuvants capable of overcoming resistance in both Gram-negative and Gram-positive pathogens. While the present investigation is limited to *in vitro* evaluation, it lays a strong experimental foundation for future mechanistic, pharmacological, and *in vivo* studies aimed at clinical translation. The integration of phytochemicals such as eugenol and hydroxychavicol into combination antimicrobial therapy represents a rational, cost-effective, and biologically sound approach to addressing the escalating global threat of antimicrobial resistance.

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